

transfer band around $25,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\log \epsilon \approx 3.5$) and a spin-allowed d-d transition band, ${}^5E_g \rightarrow {}^5T_{2g}$ around $20,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\log \epsilon \approx 2.5$). The high energy band observed in this compound may be considered as a charge transfer band, while the band at $17,300\text{ cm}^{-1}$ may be assigned to d-d transition. This broad band, occurring at lower frequency with increased intensity, indicates the lowering of symmetry of the complex from the regular octahedral geometry.

References

1. B. C. SARMA, K. R. RAY, R. E. SIEVERS and J. C. BAILAR, Jr., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, **86**, 14.
2. A. EARNshaw, E. A. KING and L. F. LARKWORTHY, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1968, 1048.
3. C. P. PRABHAKARAN and C. C. PATEL, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1969, **31**, 3316.
4. B. C. SARMA and C. C. PATEL, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1970, **8**, 94.
5. A. VAN DEN BERGEN, K. S. MURRAY, M. J. O'CONNOR and B. O. WEST, *Austral. J. Chem.*, 1969, **22**, 39.
6. B. C. SARMA and C. C. PATEL, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1970, **8**, 747.
7. K. DEY, R. L. DE and K. C. RAY, *Indian J. Chem.*, (In press).
8. J. LEWIS, F. E. MABBS and H. WEIGOLD, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1968, 1699.
9. O. T. CHRISTENSEN, *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1901, **27**, 325.
10. N. F. CURTIS, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1968, 1579.
11. K. NAKAMOTO, "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", p. 156, John Wiley and Sons, New York, 1963.
12. J. E. KOVACIC, *Spectrochim. Acta.*, 1967, **23A**, 183.
13. C. FURLANI and A. CIANO, *Anal. Chim.*, 1968, **48**, 286.

Separation of Metal E.D.T.A. Complex Ions by Paper Electrophoresis*

H. G. MUKHERJEE AND S. P. NAG

Pure Chemistry Department, University College of Science, Calcutta University

(Manuscript received 17 April 1970; revised 28 August 1971; accepted 9 February 1972)

A NUMBER of workers¹⁻³ have used electromigration in paper to separate EDTA complex ions of some metals. The present communication deals with the electrophoretic migration of some water soluble E.D.T.A. complexes using paper as supporting medium and separation of a few binary mixtures of ions in 0.05M disodium salt of E.D.T.A. carrier electrolyte.

To prepare water-soluble complexes of Cu(II), Pb(II), Bi(III), Cd(II), Fe(III), Cr(III), TiO(II), Hg(II), UO₂(II), VO(II), Ni(II), Co(II) and Tl(I) ions using Na₂-E.D.T.A. as a ligand freshly prepared metallic oxides or hydroxides were treated with 0.05M Na₂ E.D.T.A.; the solutions obtained were filtered from the excess oxides or hydroxides as the cases were and subjected to paper electrophoresis using 0.05M Na₂ E.D.T.A. as carrier electrolyte.

Durrums type⁴ vertical and Wieland and Fischer type⁵ horizontal electrophoretic sets were used for the present investigation. For the separation of anionic species horizontal type of apparatus was helpful as the negatively charged mixed ions could be applied at the cathode end of the paper strip thus increasing the possibility of the separation of these ions, due to increased length of migration. After electrophoresis the electropherograms were developed with suitable reagents and from the direction of migration it could be said that except Tl(I) and Ag(I) ions all the above mentioned ions formed stable anionic complexes. Tl(I) ion under this condition does not form stable anionic complex which is evident from its migration towards the cathode.

In order to observe whether anionic complexes of the above mentioned ions and also those of Ag(I), and UO₂(II) ions are formed during electrophoresis using 0.05M Na₂ E.D.T.A. as carrier electrolyte, simple salt solutions of these ions without prior complex formation were applied. It was found that Tl(I) ion under these conditions migrated to the cathode proving thereby its existence as cation while other ions moved to the anode as the complex MYⁿ⁻⁴ ion (where M is metal ion, n the charge on the metal ion, H₄Y. the ligand E.D.T.A.). Ag practically remained at the point of application.

TABLE I. SEPARATION OF BINARY MIXTURES OF IONS MIGRATING IN OPPOSITE DIRECTION

mixture	Time of run = 3 hr Potential gradient = 5.88 volts/cm		
	Distances of migration of the migrants		
	"+"	"o"	"-"
PbY ⁻² -Tl(I)	PbY ⁻² 3.7 cm		Tl(I) 6.2 cm
FeY ⁻ -Tl(I)	FeY ⁻ 2.1 cm		Tl(I) 6.1 cm
UO ₂ Y ⁻² -Tl(I)	UO ₂ Y ⁻² 3.8 cm		Tl(I) 6.0 cm
HgY ⁻² -Tl(I)	HgY ⁻² 4.9 cm		Tl(I) 6.0 cm
CuY ⁻² -Tl(I)	CuY ⁻² 3.7 cm		Tl(I) 6.2 cm
NiY ⁻² -Tl(I)	NiY ⁻² 3.2 cm		Tl(I) 6.1 cm
CrY ⁻ -Tl(I)	CrY ⁻ 4.8 cm		Tl(I) 6.0 cm
CoY ⁻ -Tl(I)	CoY ⁻ 3.4 cm		Tl(I) 6.0 cm
BiY ⁻ -Tl(I)	BiY ⁻ 4.9 cm		Tl(I) 6.2 cm
VOY ⁻² -Tl(I)	VOY ⁻² 4.7 cm		Tl(I) 6.2 cm
TiOY ⁻² -Tl(I)	TiOY ⁻² 5.2 cm		Tl(I) 6.0 cm

Due to these differences in the directions of migration and differential rates of movement of simple as well as complex ions, successful separations of a few binary and ternary mixtures of the above ions by paper electrophoresis using 0.05 M Na₂ E.D.T.A. as carrier electrolyte, have been achieved.

* Read at the 57th Session of the Indian Science Congress, 1970.

The sequences of separation of the migrants after electrophoretic movement at a potential gradient of 5.88 volt/cm is shown in the table where "+" sign indicates the migration to the anode, "-" sign to the cathode, ":" point of application.

TABLE 2. SEPARATION OF BINARY MIXTURES OF IONS MIGRATING IN THE SAME DIRECTION

Mixture	Distance of migration of migrants	
	":"	+"
FeY ⁻ —CuY ⁻²	FeY ⁻ ; 2.2 cm;	CuY ⁻² 3.8 cm
FeY ⁻ —VOY ⁻²	FeY ⁻ ; 2.2 cm;	VOY ⁻² 4.9 cm
FeY ⁻ —NiY ⁻²	FeY ⁻ ; 2.3 cm;	NiY ⁻² 4.0 cm
FeY ⁻ —TiOY ⁻²	FeY ⁻ ; 2.3 cm;	TiOY ⁻² 5.4 cm
BiY ⁻ —CuY ⁻²	BiY ⁻ ; 5.0 cm;	CuY ⁻² 4.0 cm

TABLE 3. SEPARATION OF TERNARY MIXTURES OF IONS
Time of run = 3 hr
Potential gradient = 5.88 volts/cm

Mixture	Distances of migration of the migrants		
	"-"	":"	+"
Tl(I)—Ag(I)—BiY ⁻	Tl(I) 6.6 cm	Ag(I) 1.2 cm	BiY ⁻ 5.4 cm
Tl(I)—Ag(I)—PbY ⁻²	Tl(I) 6.8 cm	Ag(I) 1.4 cm	PbY ⁻² 4.7 cm
Tl(I)—Ag(I)—CuY ⁻²	Tl(I) 6.8 cm	Ag(I) 1.5 cm	CuY ⁻² 4.2 cm
Tl(I)—Ag(I)—NiY ⁻²	Tl(I) 6.7 cm	Ag(I) 1.3 cm	NiY ⁻² 3.8 cm
Tl(I)—Ag(I)—CoY ⁻	Tl(I) 6.8 cm	Ag(I) 1.5 cm	CoY ⁻ 3.8 cm
Tl(I)—Ag(I)—CrY ⁻	Tl(I) 6.8 cm	Ag(I) 1.4 cm	CrY ⁻ 5.0 cm
Tl(I)—Ag(I)—VOY ⁻²	Tl(I) 6.7 cm	Ag(I) 1.4 cm	VOY ⁻² 5.1 cm
Tl(I)—Ag(I)—FeY ⁻	Tl(I) 6.8 cm	Ag(I) 1.3 cm	FeY ⁻ 2.8 cm
Tl(I)—FeY ⁻ —CuY ⁻²	Tl(I) 6.7 cm;	FeY ⁻ ; 2.7 cm;	CuY ⁻² 4.1 cm
Tl(I)—FeY ⁻ —VOY ⁻²	Tl(I) 6.8 cm;	FeY ⁻ ; 2.8 cm;	VOY ⁻² 5.0 cm
Tl(I)—FeY ⁻ —TiOY ⁻²	Tl(I) 6.8 cm	FeY ⁻ ; 2.8 cm;	TiOY ⁻² 5.7 cm

It appears from the Table 3 that the distances of migration of metal-E.D.T.A. complexes have increased to a certain extent than those shown in Tables 1 and 2. The factor of this enhanced migration are dilution, size of the drop added, concentration of the carrier electrolyte, the treatment and wetness of the paper, the temperature, voltage, the magnitude of the electro-osmotic effect and the hydrostatic flow in the paper.

Reagents used for the detection of the ions : Ag(I), Cr(III) and vanadyl ions are self indicated. Aqueous solution of KI for Tl(I); aqueous solution of chromotropic acid for TiO(II); aqueous solution of potassium-ferro-cyanide for UO₂(II) and yellow ammonium sulphide for the rest,

References

- G. H. EVANS and H. H. STRAIN, *Anal. Chim.*, 1956, **28**, 1560.
- W. M. MacNEVIN and M. L. DUNTON, *Anal. Chim.*, 1957, **29**, 1806.
- M. L. DUNTON, *Dissertation Abs.*, 1957, **17**, 970.
- H. G. MUKHERJEE, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1957, **154**, 344; 1963, **196**, 325.
- H. G. MUKHERJEE and S. P. NAG, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1969, **32**, 331; 1970, **33**, 197.

**Chalcones. Part III: Potential Germicides
Derived from 4-Hydroxy-3-Nitro-1/
Acetonaphthone**

S. S. MISRA AND R. S. TEWARI

Department of Chemistry,

Harcourt Butler Technological Institute, Kanpur

(Manuscript received 27 May 1970; accepted 3 April 1972)

DURING recent years bi- and tricyclic (naphthalene, phenanthrene, etc.) analogues of chalcones have been synthetically prepared by several investigators and tested for antimicrobial activities¹⁻⁵. In the present communication preparation and antimicrobial activity of fourteen naphthalene analogues of chalcones have been described. These compounds were synthesized by Claisen-Schmidt condensation of equimolar quantities of 4-hydroxy-3-nitro-1-acetonaphthone and required aryl aldehydes in alcoholic solution. The condensation was effected with 40% caustic potash solution at about 20-25°C (yield 63-75% except in the case of compounds No. 6, 11, 13, 14 where it varied from 40-45%). At higher temperatures the entire alcoholic mixture resinified.

TABLE 1. 4-HYDROXY-3-NITRO-1-NAPHTHYL SUBSTITUTED STYRYL KETONES

Sl No.	R	M.P.* °C	M.F.
1.	H ^a	146	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ N ₁ O ₄
2.	3-CH ₃ ^b	135	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ N ₁ O ₄
3.	4-CH ₃ ^a	126	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ N ₁ O ₄
4.	2-Cl ^b	138	C ₁₉ H ₁₂ N ₁ O ₄ Cl
5.	4-Cl ^b	176	C ₁₉ H ₁₂ N ₁ O ₄ Cl
6.	3-OH ^c	109	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ N ₁ O ₆
7.	3-OCH ₃ ^a	124	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ N ₁ O ₅
8.	4-OCH ₃ ^a	148	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ N ₁ O ₅
9.	3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂ ^a	184	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ N ₁ O ₆
10.	6-NO ₂ -3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂ ^d	114	C ₂₁ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₈
11.	2-NO ₂ ^a	224	C ₁₉ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₆
12.	4-NO ₂ ^a	155	C ₁₉ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₆
13.	2-OH-5 6-benzo ^a	146-7	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ N ₁ O ₅
14.	4-OH-3-OCH ₃ ^b	141	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ N ₁ O ₆

* All melting points are uncorrected.

^a = ethyl alcohol, ^b = ethyl acetate, ^c = 50% ethanol
^d = benzene.

The nitro benzaldehydes even at low temperatures produced dark greenish coloured masses from which no compound could be isolated. However, with 15%